

Outcome of Split Thickness Skin Graft for the Treatment of Non-Healing Foot and Leg Ulcers: A Prospective Study

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objective: The objective of our study was to evaluate the percentage of graft uptake and mean healing time of split thickness skin grafts (STSGs) in treatment of non-healing leg and foot ulcers of different etiologies and to assess the impact of non-healing ulcerations on the quality of life and the self-esteem of the patients and to evaluate whether STSGs for ulcers will have positive impact on patient's quality of life and self-esteem.

Materials and Methods: This is a prospective clinical observational study conducted in the department of general surgery, Government Kilpauk Medical College and Hospital from January 2016 to September 2016 on 49 patients selected by random sampling method. Percentage of graft uptake and mean healing time, HAQ-8 score and RSES score, both preoperatively and postoperatively were measured and recurrence, if any, was also noted.

Result: A total of 49 patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers of various etiology (diabetes mellitus, venous, trauma, burns) who met the inclusion criteria for this study were included in this study ranging of average age 50.55 years. Thirty-two (65.3%) patients were male and seventeen (34.7%) patients were female. There was a significant difference between the graft uptake and the mean healing time with an inverse relationship ($P < 0.0001$). The present study showed there is a significant improvement in both quality of life as measured by HAQ-8 scale and self-esteem of the patient as measured by RSES scale after application of split-thickness skin graft for non-healing leg and foot ulcer patients.

Conclusion: The present study concluded that STSGs is a simple, effective way for faster healing of ulcerations and it helps in improvement of quality of life and self-esteem of the patients.

Keywords: split thickness skin graft, non-healing leg and foot ulcers, wound healing.

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Introduction

Ulcer is a break in a continuity of an epithelial surface which is characterized by progressive destruction of surface epithelium and healing by formation of granulation tissue at base [1,2]. Ulcers may be caused due to various etiologies. Non-healing ulcers are those which do not improve after four weeks or does not heal after eight weeks. More commonly non-healing ulcers are caused by chronic venous disorders, diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disorders [1,2].

These lower limb non-healing ulcers is a debilitating phenomenon by not only affecting the patient directly such as physical pain, loss of movements, etc., it has major impact on the economy, since a major amount of resources are spent every year to treat and prevent the disease. These ulcers, with its severity and morbidity, also a major cause of loss of work of patients. Patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers had

significantly more pain, more restrictions regarding social functioning, less vitality, and limitations with respect to emotional roles compared to the general population. Other problem areas identified were restrictions in work capacity, recreation, social interaction, psychological well-being and so leg ulceration has an impact on patient's Quality of Life, national guidelines on the treatment of leg ulceration need to more specifically address these far-ranging effects of these ulcerations and to improve the care of the patients.

Split-thickness skin grafts (STSG) have withstood the test of time as a method for soft tissue coverage in open wounds of many etiologies. STSG is a simple and minimally invasive procedure for the management of foot ulcers and the most common performed procedures to close defects unable to be closed with the simple approximation of the wound edges. Skin grafts are used to heal a gap in the skin.

If one can join the edges of a wound together without too much tension by stitching or stapling, then so much the better, but the size of the wound is often so great that it is impossible to join the edges of the wound together and if left to heal by itself it would heal very slowly. Despite having its own limitations and recent developments of artificial skin, skin grafting continues to be valuable tool for closure of soft tissue coverage.

Hence split-thickness skin grafting is a way of effective management of non-healing ulcers of leg and foot and by this method patient can achieve a faster healing time compared to conventional methods like dressings alone, and by improving the healing time in turn can help in improving the patient's quality of life, self-esteem and decrease the economic burden of the country as a whole.

Aim of the Study

1. To determine the result of split-thickness skin graft (STSG) for the treatment of non-healing leg and foot ulcers.
2. To assess the graft uptake (GU) and mean healing time depending on the age, size of ulcer and comorbidities of the patients.
3. To assess the quality of life after application of split-thickness skin grafting for patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers.
4. To assess the self-esteem after application of split-thickness skin grafting for patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers.
5. To assess the recurrence of ulcer.

Reasons for Conducting the Study

1. Non-healing leg ulcers becoming major health problem recently and it pose major impact on the social, physical, and psychological aspects of the patients.
2. Disability, lengthy hospitalization, multiple procedures, prolonged rehabilitation, low quality of life, loss of job and income pose enormous financial burden and affects chronic ulcer victim adversely.
3. Split-thickness skin grafting is widely accepted method for soft tissue coverage, though number of wound care products and synthetic grafts are available, STSG remain gold standard first line treatment for lower extremity wounds.
4. To assess how STSG application improves quality of life and self-esteem of the patients.

Materials and Methods:

This is a prospective clinical observational study conducted in the department of general surgery, Government Kilpauk Medical College and Hospital from January 2016 to September 2016 on 49 patients selected by random sampling method. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional

ethical committee prior to commencement of the study.

Inclusion criteria:

- All patients with non-healing foot and leg ulcers.
- Patients of both sexes.
- Patients between age 18 and 80 years.
- Patients given written informed consent.
- Patients willing for surgery.
- Patients willing to come for regular follow up for 6 months.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients of leg and foot ulcers < 5 cm² in size.
- Patients with ulcers, slough, and unhealthy tissues.
- Ulcers over plantar aspect.
- Patients with bleeding diathesis.
- Patients with vascular insufficiency/occlusion.
- Wounds with exposed bone or cartilage.
- Patients not fit for surgery.
- Patients not willing for surgery.

Data Collection:

49 patients were chosen based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Clinical assessment was done at time of inclusion in the study. Basic routine investigations like complete haemogram, blood sugar-fasting and postprandial, serum creatinine and blood urea, serum electrolytes, bleeding time, clotting time, pus culture and sensitivity, X-ray local region, doppler study of involved limb and serum proteins (HIV, HBsAg, anti-HCV) were done for all patients.

Informed consent of all the patients were obtained for inclusion under the study. Patients who met the preoperative criteria were posted for surgery. Graft uptake and mean healing time were determined post-operatively. Quality of life and self-esteem of the patients were assessed using Stanford health assessment scale HAQ-8 and Rosenberg self-esteem scale RSES, both preoperatively and post operatively. Recurrence of the ulcer was noted, if any, post-operatively. Local examination of ulcer included site, size, number, shape, floor, edge, margin, base, depth, discharge and regional lymphadenopathy, peripheral pulses. Abdominal examination as well as cardiovascular and respiratory system examination was performed.

Eligibility Criteria for Application of STSG

1. Wounds should be well vascularized.
2. Non-infected wound bed- negative for microbial culture.
3. Healthy granulation tissue denotes better nutritional status and overall well-being of the patient.

4. Hypertrophic granulation tissue should be flattened or trimmed to improve graft uptake and epithelial migration.
5. Epithelial migration at the edges of the wound indicates the bed is ready for skin grafting.
6. Culture specific antibiotic, serial thorough debridement and daily dressings play major role in preparation of the recipient bed for grafting.
7. Wound should not have any bone or tendon exposed.

Surgical Steps of Split-Thickness Skin Grafting

Prophylactic antibiotics were administered just before starting the procedure and spinal anesthesia was given for adequate pain control.

Preparation of Donor Site

We commonly used anterior or lateral aspect of the thigh for taking graft. Betadine solution is used for preparing the donor site and it was washed off with saline and dried. Donor site properly draped with sterile towels. A sterile lubricant, we use liquid paraffin as a lubricant, was applied to the donor site and to the Humby instrument which was used to take graft.

Preparation of Recipient Site

Recipient bed was cleaned. Superficial sloughs, if present, were removed and unhealthy areas also were removed. Like donor area, recipient bed also was prepared using betadine and washed with saline. And recipient area was properly draped with sterile towel. Bed was scraped with the edge of knife to decrease the amount of contamination. Granulation tissue flattened and rinsed with saline. Recipient bed after preparation was covered with sterile pads to decrease contamination.

Harvesting Graft from Donor Site

Good preparation of donor site was done. Blade was inserted in the Humby knife and settings adjusted approximately at 0.4mm. Assistant keeps the donor site flattens and spread out by placing tension on the donor skin using gauze.

The Humby knife was held with its edge placed at about 45 degree angle with the donor skin. Graft harvesting started by a back and forth motion of knife over the tight skin and progressed till desired amount of the graft was taken and the graft was cut off using blade.

And the harvested graft was placed in the saline tray.

Figure 1: Preparation of the graft

Preparation of the graft – With the help of the assistant graft sheet is spread out and hand meshing was done using no.11 blade mounted in no.3 Bard-Parkers handle. After meshing, the graft was washed in saline solution.

Placement of graft onto the recipient site – The meshed graft was placed with its dermis side over the recipient bed and was fixed using intermittent stay sutures using 3-0 ethilon with long tail.

Application of dressing – A layer of liquid paraffin gauze was applied to the graft site. And sterile pads were placed over it and dressing done. Depending on the site of grafting, patient was given plaster of paris application to immobilize the area. Donor site raw area was covered with sterile moist gauze and sterile compression dressing was done.

Postoperative Care: Patients were maintained on I.V. fluids on 1st post-operative day. All patients

were maintained on third generation cephalosporins.

From 2nd post-operative day patients were started on oral diets. Patients with comorbidities like Diabetes, hypertension, coronary artery disease were started on respective drugs on the same day evening of surgery.

Wound Assessment: All wounds were inspected on 3rd and 5th Postoperative day and patients were discharged on 6th or 7th postoperative day. And patients were followed up as outpatient basis twice weekly for first two months and then monthly till 6 months. Recurrence of ulcers was noted, if present, during the 6 month follow up.

Quality Of Life: Functional status was evaluated using the 8-item short version of the Stanford Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ-8) [3]. This instrument measures the difficulty in performing activities of daily living. For each item, there is a 4-level difficulty scale that is scored from 0 to 3. The eight item scores are averaged into an overall score on a scale from 0 (no disability) to 3 (completely disabled). Analyzed preoperatively and postoperatively after complete healing occurs. (Given to patient in native language)

Self-Esteem: Self-esteem was assessed by the Brazilian version of the Rosenberg Self-Esteem scale (RSE/UNIFESP-EPM), [4] which consists of 10 items rated on a 4-point scale. The total RSE score ranges from 0 to 30 (30 = highest self-esteem level and 0 = lowest self-esteem level). Analyzed preoperatively and postoperatively after complete healing occurs. (Given to patient in native language).

Data Analysis

Data of 49 patients were entered into the Microsoft excel sheet. The values were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 19. Normality of the data was checked using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The paired student t-test was used to analyze the values collected before and after the surgery. The mean of the above values, the standard deviation, standard error of mean and the P-value were calculated. The results were converted into pie charts, bar diagrams and scatter map for the sake of easy understanding.

Results

A total of 49 patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers of various etiology (diabetes mellitus, venous, trauma, burns) who met the inclusion criteria for this study were included in this study ranging from 29 to 70 years (average age – 50.55). Six patients (12.2%) were in age group less than 40 years, thirty-five patients (71.5%) in age group between 40 and 60 years, and eight patients (16.3%) in age group more than 60 years (Chart 1). Thirty-two (65.3%) patients were male and seventeen (34.7%) patients were female (Chart 2). Mean age of male was 50.25 years and mean age of female was 51.1 years. All 49 patients were available for post-operative follow-up for 6 months. The cause of non-healing ulcers was diabetes mellitus in 34 (69.4%) patients, traumatic in 8 (16.3%) patients, venous disease in 6 (12.3%) patients, and burns in 1 (2%) patient (Chart 3). Among these patients five (10.2%) had coronary artery disease, two (4.1%) patients were hypertensive, twelve (24.5%) patients had no comorbidities.

Chart 1: Age distribution

Chart 2: Sex ratio

Chart 3: Ulcer etiology

All diabetic patients (69.4%) were maintained on injection insulin for glycemic control and patients were posted for STSG application only after achieving proper glycemic control and obtaining fitness for surgery from diabetologist/physician. Similarly, hypertensive patients (4.1%) were maintained on oral anti-hypertensive drugs and after achieving proper blood pressure control patients were posted for surgery. For patients with coronary artery disease, echocardiogram was done and after obtaining cardiologists fitness patients were taken up for STSG application. All CAD patients who were taking tab. clopidogrel were asked to withhold the drug for 5 days prior to surgery and were taken up surgery. Patients with

ulcers due to venous disorder (12.3%) had their venous system completely assessed by Doppler study, duplex scan and definitive procedure for venous disorder was done before patient was posted for STSG application. All patients were assessed for peripheral vascular competency by Arterial Doppler study and patients only with adequate peripheral blood supply were posted for surgery. Patients with insufficient peripheral blood supply were not included for the study. All patients were subjected to wound culture and sensitivity, and were treated with antibiotics according to the culture and sensitivity report and after obtaining negative wound culture, patients were taken up for the procedure. The average ulcer size prior to graft

procedure was 54.24 cm² (ranging from 15 to 124 cm²). About thirteen (26.5%) patients had ulcer size <25 cm², thirty patients (61.2%) had ulcer size 25-100 cm², and six patients (12.3%) had ulcer size >100 cm² (Chart 4).

After split-thickness skin graft application, wounds were inspected under sterile aseptic precautions on 3th and 5th post-operative day. Graft uptake on 3rd post-operative day was 80% in one patient (2%),

85% in two patients (4.1%), 90% in six patients (12.2%), 95% in twelve patients (24.5%), 100% in twenty-eight patients (57.2%) (Chart 5).

Graft uptake on 5th post-operative day was 80% in two patients (4.1%), 85% in four patients (8.2%), 90% in eight patients (16.3%), 95% in seventeen patients (34.7%), 100% in eighteen patients (36.7%) (Chart 5).

Chart 4: Ulcer size

Chart 5: Graft update percentage

Chart 6: Duration of wound healing

Chart 7: Comorbidities and healing time

Chart 8: Age and mean of healing time

Chart 9: Ulcer size and wound healing time

Chart 10: Graft update percentage and duration of wound healing

Chart 11: Percentage of recurrence

Chart 12: Quality of life chart

Chart 13: Self-esteem chart

Table 1: Analysis of HAQ-8 and RSES score

	Pre OP HAQ-8 Score	Post OP HAQ-8 Score	Pre OP RSES Score	Post OP RSES Score
Mean	23.5102	11.26531	13.87755	22.59185
Median	24	11	14	23
Standard Deviation	2.08289	1.91241	1.727627	2.090837
Standard Error Of Mean	0.29755	0.273201	0.296804	0.298699
P	<0.0001		<0.0001	

Table 2: Analysis of healing time

S.no	Parameters	n	%	Mean healing time in weeks	P Value
1	Age<40	6	12.2	6.1	<0.0001
2	Age 40-60	35	71.5	7.2	
3	Age>60	8	16.3	9.2	
4	Ulcer size<25cm ²	13	26.5	6.2	<0.0001
5	Ulcer size 25-100 cm ²	30	61.2	7.2	
6	Ulcer size>100cm ²	6	12.3	9.1	
7	Comorbidities DM, HTN, CAD	37	75.5	7.2	0.209
8	No comorbidities	12	24.5	7.2	
9	Graft uptake <90%	6	12.3	10.1	<0.0001
10	Graft uptake 90-100%	43	83.7	7	

The complete wound healing time was calculated in weeks which varied from 3 weeks to 12 weeks with mean healing time of 7.2 weeks. The complete wound healing was three weeks in two patients (4.1%), five weeks in four patients (8.2%), six weeks in fifteen patients (30.6%), seven weeks in thirteen patients (26.5%), eight weeks in seven patients (14.3%), nine weeks in two patients (4.1%), ten weeks in three patients (6.1%), eleven weeks in two patients (4.1%), twelve weeks in one patient (2%). (Chart 6)

In our study there was no significant difference in the mean healing time in patients with comorbidities (37 patients- 75.5%) and patients with no comorbidities (12 patients- 24.5%) as identified by data analysis (P=0.209) (Chart 7 and Table 2).

Our study, however, showed statistical significance between the age of the patients and mean healing time in weeks (P=<0.0001). The mean healing time was 6.1 weeks in patients less than 40 years (6 patients-12.2%), 7.2 weeks in patients between 40 and 60 years (35 patients- 71.5%), and 9.2 weeks in patients above 60 years of age (8 patients-16.3%). There was increase in mean healing time with increasing age of the patient (Chart 8 and Table 2).

And our study also identified a significant difference in mean healing time according to the size of the ulcer (P=<0.0001). Thirteen patients (26.5%) with ulcer size less than 25 cm² had mean healing time of 6.2 weeks, thirty patients (61.2%) with ulcer size between 25 and 100 cm² had mean healing time of 7.2 weeks, and six patients (12.3%) with ulcer size more than 100 cm² had mean healing time of 9.1 weeks (Chart 9 and Table 2). The above data shows that the mean healing time increases with increase in the ulcer size.

There was a significant difference between the graft uptake and the mean healing time with an inverse relationship (P=<0.0001). Patients with graft uptake 80% at 5th post-operative day (2 patients-4.1%) had mean healing time of 10.2 weeks, and with 85% (4 patients-8.2%) had 10.1 weeks, with 90% (8 patients-16.3%) had 7.5 weeks, with 95% (17 patients- 34.7%) had 7.1 weeks, and

with 100% (18 patients- 36.7%) had 6.5 weeks. These data suggest that patient with better graft uptake has faster healing time (Chart 10).

And in our study only two patients (4.1%) had recurrence of ulcer and other forty-seven (95.9%) patients did not have any recurrence during 6 month follow up. Those two patients were conservatively managed. Of the two patients one patient was diabetic and other had no comorbidities (Chart 11).

All patients were subjected for questionnaire (In native language) examination in their native language during preoperative period to assess the quality of life and self-esteem of patients with non-healing leg and foot ulcers using Stanford Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ-8) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale 1965 (RSES) respectively.

Quality of life was assessed using HAQ-8 scale and the values ranged from 20 to 28 with mean value of 23.5 and self-esteem assessed using RSES scale and the values ranged from 11 to 18 with mean value of 13.8. All patients were subjected for STSG application and after achieving complete wound healing, which varied among individuals, were again subjected to the same questionnaire which was given preoperatively and values were evaluated. Post-operative values of HAQ-8 scale ranged from 8 to 15 with mean value of 11.2 and RSES scale ranged from 18 to 26 with mean value of 22.5 (Chart 12 and 13).

The above values were analyzed statistically and our study showed significant difference in both HAQ-8 (P<0.0001) and RSES (P<0.0001) values measured preoperative and postoperatively. By above data our study showed there is a significant improvement in both quality of life as measured by HAQ-8 scale and self-esteem of the patient as measured by RSES scale after application of split-thickness skin graft for non-healing leg and foot ulcer patients. (Table 1)

Discussion

This is a prospective observational study on the outcome of split-thickness grafting for the treatment of non-healing ulcers of leg and foot

conducted from January 2016 to September 2016. The inferences derived were compared with similar studies and discussed below.

In our study percentage of male patients were higher about 65.3% compared to female patients 34.7%. Highest percentage of non-healing ulcer patients was in age group between 40-60 years constituting 71.5%. Percentage of male patients was highest compared to female patients in all age groups. Highest percentage of male patients of about 44.9% was in age group 40-60 years.

Cornwall et al [2] in their study stated about 70% of the patient were over the age of 70 years. In our study 53% was above 50 years and 47% were below 50 years. Callum MJ [1] in their study mentioned that not only elderly population was at risk of developing ulceration and in their study ulceration were noted in 22% patients before age of 40 years. In our study also there was 12.2% population who developed ulcerations before age of 40 years.

The number of elderly patients above 50 years developing ulcerations was 53% in our study and it can be attributed to poor financial conditions, illiteracy, general debility, low socioeconomic status, poor nutrition resulting in less immunity and subsequently patients are prone for infection and development of ulcerations.

Our study showed statistical significance between the age of the patients and mean healing time in weeks ($P < 0.0001$). The mean healing time was 6.1 weeks in patients less than 40 years (6 patients-12.2%), 7.2 weeks in patients between 40 and 60 years (35 patients- 71.5%), and 9.2 weeks in patients above 60 years of age (8 patients-16.3%). There was increase in mean healing time with increasing age of the patient. To support this Jankunas et al [5] has both stated that patient's age has impact of ulcer healing and success rates. But Oyibo et al [6] stated patient's age has no role in healing time.

And also our study did not show any significant difference in healing time between male and female patients. Male patients had mean healing time of 7.2 weeks compared to female patients in whom it was 8 weeks. This was however against Marston [7] who mentioned female gender has improved healing time. Oyibo et al [6] stated there is no gender difference in terms of healing time. To support the above data that graft size, donor and recipient location, patient age, gender, and race did not affect graft survival were mentioned by Ramanujam et al [8] in their study. In study by Rose et al [9], according to the Cox regression model, baseline wound size and patient age were not significant predictors of healing time.

The most common type of ulcer in our study was diabetes mellitus in 34 (69.4%) patients, followed by traumatic in 8 (16.3%) patients, and then by venous disease in 6 (12.3%) patients, and burns in 1 (2%) patient. According to study done by Gilliland [10], 95% of leg ulcers were due to vascular etiology and among all chronic wounds in the lower extremity, venous ulcer dominated the differential diagnosis, accounting for up to 90% of the cases. Sundresh NJ et al [11] in their study grafted 26% traumatic, 38% healing, 14% burn, 8% diabetic, 6 % scar ulcers and 2 % each of infective (cellulites) and bed sore ulcer patients. However, in our study highest percentage grafted was diabetic wound around 69.4% followed by traumatic 16.3%, venous 12.3%, and burns 2%.

The above difference is because all most studies were done in western population. However, our study has been carried in our country and we included only those ulcer patients who underwent split skin grafting. Hence our study doesn't present the actual incidence of ulcers with different etiology but the distribution of ulcers of different etiologies which undergo split skin grafting.

In our study there were 37 patients with comorbidities including diabetes mellitus, hypertension and coronary artery disease (75.5%) and 12 patients with no comorbidities (24.5%).

In study by Ribu et al [12] conducted on 127 diabetic patients at 1 year follow up only 37% were healed making diabetic patients having poor prognosis for STSGs. And Thourani et al [13] also stated diabetes mellitus has impact on success rate of STSGs. Rosenberg [14] also stated that diabetic complications have an impact on wound healing which can adversely affect STSGs.

However, in our study there was no significant difference in the mean healing time in patients with comorbidities (37 patients- 75.5%) and patients with no comorbidities (12 patients- 24.5%) as identified by data analysis ($P=0.209$). This goes in line with Rose et al [15] observed no significant difference in wound-healing time between those with and without diabetes.

The above difference may be attributed to the smaller population of our study and only patients who underwent STSGs (with no complications associated with comorbid illness) were included in our study. Bitsch et al [16] stated that healing rates were better for traumatic ulcers compared to other ulcers but our study healing time was similar in all etiologies and this again attributed to smaller number of patients and unequal distribution of etiologies than studies mentioned above.

And our study also identified a significant difference in mean healing time according to the size of the ulcer ($P < 0.0001$). Thirteen patients

(26.5%) with ulcer size less than 25 cm² had mean healing time of 6.2 weeks, thirty patients (61.2%) with ulcer size between 25 and 100 cm² had mean healing time of 7.2 weeks, and six patients (12.3%) with ulcer size more than 100 cm² had mean healing time of 9.1 weeks. This data is supported by Oyibo et al [6] who reported that the greater the cross-sectional area of the wound, the more likely it was for patients to experience difficulty healing or to require amputation.

In our study we found significant difference between the graft uptake and the mean healing time with an inverse relationship ($P < 0.0001$). Patients with graft uptake 80% at 5th post-operative day (2 patients-4.1%) had mean healing time of 10.2 weeks, and with 85% (4 patients-8.2%) had 10.1 weeks, with 90% (8 patients-16.3%) had 7.5 weeks, with 95% (17 patients- 34.7%) had 7.1 weeks, and with 100% (18 patients- 36.7%) had 6.5 weeks. These data suggest that patient with better graft uptake has faster healing time. However, Mahmoud SM et al [17] in their study recorded 100% skin graft take in 84% of the patients on the fifth postoperative day and in 62% on weeks 3 and 8 and mentioned statistically significant reduction in mean hospital stay and healing time for those patients treated with STSG. And also Anderson et al [18] stated those patients with less than 95% graft take had a significantly longer healing time than those with greater than 95% graft take ($P < 0.001$) which goes in line with our study.

In our study all patients were given preoperative antibiotics according to culture and sensitivity of the wound and were only posted for surgery if wound culture becomes negative for microbial culture and patients were also given antibiotics just before surgery and it was supported by Høgsberg et al [19], Unal et al [20], Wilson et al [21] who stated the preoperative infections leads to rejection/failure of grafts. Also Henderson et al [22] reported that prophylactic antibiotic plays major role in graft outcome.

In our study we used only meshed grafts which were supported by Kirsner et al [23] who stated "that meshed split-thickness skin grafting is a safe and effective therapy for recalcitrant lower extremity ulcers." However, Puttirutvong et al [24] stated no significant difference between meshed and non-meshed graft."

In our study only two patients had recurrence and one of them was diabetic and other had no comorbidities. Those two patients were treated conservatively. Bitsch et al [16] stated that recurrence rates were more for venous ulcer and less for traumatic ulcers. But in our study no significance can be made out because of less recurrence rate and it was not attributable to particular etiology as mentioned in above studies

since our study had unequal incidence of ulcer etiology and smaller sample size.

All patients were subjected to quality-of-life assessment and self-esteem examination both preoperatively and post operatively by questionnaire method using HAQ-8 and RSES scale respectively. Our study showed significant difference in both HAQ-8 ($P < 0.0001$) and RSES ($P < 0.0001$) values measured preoperative and postoperatively. This data suggest that patient had significant improvement in the quality of life and self-esteem after treatment of their non-healing ulcers and in our study by means of STSG application. On reviewing literature number of studies supported our above data.

Several studies [25,26,28,29,30-34] have revealed that chronic non-healing ulcers of lower extremities pose a major health problem and significantly affects patients functional, psychological and physical abilities and leads to poor health related quality of life and self-esteem of the patients compared to those who has no ulcerations. And they also have mentioned with proper intervention and healing of ulcers there was significant improvement in the quality of life and self-esteem of the patients. In our study, the interventions were application of STSG for non-healing ulcers and we found a significant improvement in the quality of life and self-esteem of the patients.

Some authors [17,18,35-38] have reported that for a non-healing ulcers skin grafting, commonly split-thickness skin grafting is an easy, simple, versatile, technique for a wound coverage, which is large in size and tends to heal slowly without any interventions, resulting in sensate and functional limb and also provides better outcome.

Conclusion

Our study revealed a significant role for split-thickness skin grafts (STSGs) in the treatment of non-healing foot and leg ulcers. This intervention had a positive impact on patients' quality of life and self-esteem. Importantly, our findings suggest that the patient's age and ulcer size are factors that influence wound healing, while comorbidities and gender do not appear to play a significant role.

In conclusion, STSGs provide a simple and effective approach for faster healing of ulcerations, leading to an improvement in the quality of life and self-esteem of patients. These findings highlight the necessity of treating non-healing ulcers at earlier stages. However, the treatment should not stop at the surgical intervention. Instead, a multidisciplinary approach is required to address the various aspects of non-healing ulcers and achieve the best possible outcomes for the patients.

Abbreviations

- STSG – Split-thickness skin graft
- FTSG – Full-thickness skin graft
- SSG – Split skin grafting
- DM – Diabetes mellitus
- HTN – Hypertension
- CAD – Coronary artery disease
- GU – Graft uptake
- HAQ-8 – Health assessment questionnaire-8
- RSES – Rosenberg self-esteem scale
- PDGF – Platelet derived growth factor
- TGF β – Transforming growth factor beta
- PMN – Polymorphonuclear leukocytes
- EGF – Epithelial growth factor
- VEGF – Vascular endothelial growth factor
- PRE OP – Pre operative
- POST OP – Post operative

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